

Overview of Impacts of Financial Management on Activities of Public Educational Institutions in Vietnam

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Abstract:

Renovating the financial management mechanism for higher education institutions and public is a strategic goal of our State in recent times. Financial management plays a very important role in the operation of public universities and colleges in Vietnam. The objective of the article is to review studies on the impact of financial management on the performance of public educational institutions, specifically universities and colleges in Vietnam. From there, recommend solutions to help improve the efficiency of financial management in public non-business units in general.

Keywords: Financial management, educational activities, colleges, public universities

1. Introduction

Renovating the financial management mechanism for public educational institutions in the direction of increasing autonomy and self-responsibility is in line with the international trend and major policy of our Party and State in recent years.

Currently, the regulations on financial management mechanism for public colleges in the trend of transitioning to vocational education mechanism are quite complete such as: Law on Education; Decree No. 75/2006/ND-CP dated August 2, 2006 of the Government stipulating and guiding the implementation of the Law on Education, Decree No. 43/2006/ND-CP dated April 25, 2006 of the Government regulating determine the autonomy, self-responsibility for tasks, organizational apparatus, payroll and finance for public non-business units; Decree No. 16/2015/ND-CP dated February 14, 2015 stipulating the autonomy mechanism of public non-business units; Decree No. 48/2015/ND-CP dated May 15, 2015 detailing a number of articles of the Law on Vocational Education...

The objective of the financial management mechanism for public colleges is to increase the autonomy and self-responsibility in the organization, arrange the apparatus, use labor and financial resources, improve quality, and increase revenue. , income for employees, gradually reducing subsidies for state budget.

Subjects assigned the right to financial management of public colleges are divided into 3 types: Units with non-business revenue that can cover all expenses for regular activities; Units with non-business revenue sources can cover part of the expenses for regular activities by themselves; The unit has low non-business income or is supported 100% of expenses for regular operations. In addition, the financial management mechanism includes the following basic contents:

- Autonomy in management and exploitation of revenue: Public colleges' revenues are the funds received by the school that are not required to be refunded according to the provisions of the law, serving training, scientific research and activities. Other activities of public colleges, including: Revenue from state budget Grants, Revenue from school career activities; Revenues from aid, gifts, donations and other sources of income. Financial management allows schools to exploit and manage revenue sources in accordance with the law and must be transparent about their finances.

- Autonomy in spending management: Expenditures of public colleges are expenditures deployed for the school's operations, including: recurrent and irregular expenses. The requirement for autonomy in spending management is to ensure scientific norms and standards that are reasonable, economical, accurate, honest and effective.

Public colleges are allowed to increase revenue sources to increase additional income for officials and employees according to internal spending regulations. In addition, public colleges are allowed to set aside funds for career development, bonus and welfare funds, and income stabilization reserves...

- Autonomy in management and use of school assets: Public colleges are assigned autonomy in purchasing and exploiting assets, improving productivity and efficiency in using assets, expanding revenue generation for the school... ensure that the school's operations both improve thrift and reduce waste in asset management and use.

2. Theoretical foundations of financial management of public educational institutions

Financial management concept

Management concept in the Textbook of Management Science (Academy of Finance) "is an organized and targeted influence of the management subjects on the managed objects and objects in order to use the most effective resources and opportunities of the organization to achieve its goals in an ever-changing environment" [70]. Also according to scientists at the Academy of Finance, the influence of the manager on the managed object is "conducted through the use of appropriate tools and methods in order to influence and control the managed object." manage development activities in accordance with objective laws and achieve the set goals" [68, p.39].

According to the management theory of modern managers, "Management is knowing exactly what you want people to do, and then understanding that they get the job done in the best and cheapest way." (F. Taylor); "Management is an art of achieving a set goal through directing, directing, coordinating, and directing the activities of others" (Harol Koontz). Paul Hersey and KenBlanc Heard in their book "Human Resource Management" argue that "Management is a process of working together between managers and those being managed in order to mobilize through individual and group activities and mobilize other resources to achieve organizational goals". Meanwhile, approaching the management process, Stephen P. Robbins and Mary Coulter (2011) stated that "Management is the process of planning, organizing, leading and controlling the activities of the members in the organization. organization and use all other resources of the organization to achieve its objectives" [152].

Author Luong Thi Huyen [85] gave the definition "Management is a way, measure and principle affecting human activities in order to achieve the set goals with the desired effect".

Thus, it can be seen that management is a characteristic activity of human society, but more specifically, it is a characteristic of human-owned (organized and controlled) systems, aiming at goals. certain target. And therefore, in management activities, the issues of (i) management subjects, (ii) management objects, (iii) management objectives, (iv) management tools and methods are the the central factor, which requires proper research and identification. In terms of expression, management activities are conducted through an iterative process of five stages: (1) planning work, (2) organization of the apparatus (oraganization), (3) implementation (realization), (4) checking the implementation of the plan (controlizatn), and (5) summarization. In management science, people emphasize the following two issues: firstly, after determining the plan, the organizational apparatus plays the most important role in determining the success of the implementation of the plan. Secondly, in the process of organizing and implementing, management science attaches great importance to indirect impact measures through ideological education, awareness raising, organization of emulation movements, social welfare activities. ... in order to create consensus, promote the completion of the system's goals.

Finance is a familiar concept that has been researched and clarified by many scientists in textbooks, theses and research works from different perspectives. According to scientists at the Academy of Finance, "Finance is an economic category, reflecting the distributional relations of social wealth in the form of value, arising in the process of creating, distributing and using use the monetary funds of actors in the economy to achieve the

objectives of the subjects under certain conditions" [68], or "Finance is a method of mobilizing, allocating and using scarce resources. scarce resources (financial resources) in order to meet the needs of stakeholders in socio-economic development" [69, p.59]. With the same point of view, scientists at the National Economics University have stated the concept "Finance is an objective economic category, associated with commodity economy and market economy. It is a system of certain economic relations expressed in the form of money, arising in the process of forming, managing and using monetary funds in order to develop production, improve material life and the spirit of the people" [127]. Approaching according to the nature of finance and associated with political institutions in Vietnam, "Our country's finance is a system of economic relations that manifests itself in the formation, distribution and use of monetary funds in national economy in order to build, protect and develop socialism".

When researching on the financial management mechanism for high-quality training programs in public colleges in Vietnam, author Nguyen Thu Huong [83] said that "Finance is an economic category that, expressing the economic relationship between entities to form, manage and use monetary funds to achieve the goals of managers and related entities". According to author Luong Thi Huyen [85], "Finance is understood as the movement of monetary capital, it reflects the synthesis of economic relations arising in the creation or use of monetary funds to meet the different needs of subjects in society".

According to the above points of view, finance is understood as an objective economic category, reflecting the interaction between actors in the economic system to create, allocate and use monetary funds to achieve the goals of the financial system. socio-economic development goals set out.

Therefore, the author believes that financial management is an activity of actors in society through the use of a certain logical sequence of management tools and methods to influence and control the activities of the society. finance, in order to achieve the goals set out in each specific socio-economic development stage.

At the same time, approaching from a systematic point of view and associated with the research orientation of the thesis topic, the financial management described as follows is appropriate:

Firstly, financial management is a system, with elements, the relationships/interactions between elements are considered from different perspectives associated with central issues/factors of management activities. financial management. Whereby:

(i) Financial management is an activity of actors in society, so the elements of the financial management system are subjects in society that have an interrelationship, which is shown through compromise between the rights - common interests of the subjects and the rights - interests of each subject in the process of using management tools and methods to influence and control financial activities; and the rationale for this compromise comes from the role and position (position of power) of each subject in the system (hierarchy of authority, responsibility in the system). In which, the role of an entity is a form of expression of the status (position of power) of the entity through the performance of one or more functions that the entity must perform in the system. In other words, the role of an entity is a category to express the allowed interaction of that entity with other entities in the system; given by the activities, the behavior of that entity with respect to the system corresponds to the position of that entity in the system [56, p.43];

(ii) Financial management is the use in a certain logical sequence of management tools and methods to influence and control financial activities, so the element of the financial management system is management tools and methods, but more specifically legal norms, technical regulations, ethical codes, economic leverage (taxes, prices, credit interest rates, etc.) financial impact and control; at the same time, it is the use of management tools and methods in a certain logical sequence that shows the relationship/interaction between the tools (elements) and management methods (of the system);

(iii) The object of financial management is financial activities, so the elements of the financial management system are activities of creation, distribution and use of monetary funds; the interaction between these elements/operations is a cause-and-effect relationship;

(iv) Management in general and financial management in particular always exist associated with certain goals, so the element of the financial management system is a set/system of objectives that the subject manages. set out in accordance with each specific development stage/pathway, and thus each goal is both a cause and an effect of another (this interaction between goals is the mechanism of the goal system). pepper).

Second, the (general) goal of the financial management system is to ensure that financial activities operate in accordance with the objective laws of socio-economic development, and the subjective wishes of the owners. manageable in society.

Third, the financial management system is always fluctuating and changing to adapt to the objective laws of socio-economic development.

Thus, the concept of financial management can be stated as follows: Financial management is the interaction between actors in society on the basis of the relationship of rights - interests of the parties, which is expressed through the use of a certain logical sequence of management tools and methods, to influence and control the relevant financial activity, in order to achieve the stated objectives (the common objectives of the financial institutions). individual subjects and goals of each participant in the mechanism) in each specific development stage/process.

Applying the above concept, and with the research orientation of the thesis topic, then: Financial management of public colleges is the interaction between the state, the school and other entities in society. (students, learners' families, businesses,...) on the basis of the relationship of rights - interests of the parties, expressed through the use of a certain logical sequence (hierarchical authority) management tools and methods, to influence and control the creation, allocation and use of financial resources, contributing to strengthening the financial management of public colleges in the current conditions. now on. In which, the main management tools and methods are used by the State to influence and control financial activities, which are:

Management tools:

(1) Legal tools include: legal documents and legal documents. This is always considered as the most important tool of the state for social management in general, and the management of financial resources from state budget investment/funding for public colleges in particular, shows the true nature. The "socialist rule of law state", "the state that manages society by the Constitution and laws" has been affirmed in the Constitution of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam in 2013. Adopting a system of documents legal documents (such as: Law on state budget; Law on Fees and Charges; Law on Public Investment; Law on Taxation; regulations on decentralization of responsibilities between budget levels in investment and development of public higher education; regulations the process of planning and estimating financial resources for public colleges;...), the state adjusts and orients the stable development of public colleges; creating an effective legal basis for realizing equality of rights and obligations among entities, in order to improve the efficiency of investment in the development of public colleges, and to ensure social progress and justice.

(2) The planning tool is a system that includes many contents such as: development strategy; development Planning; medium-term plan (3 years or 5 years); annual plan; programme; project and budget plan. This is a management tool that exists not only in socialist countries, developed capitalist countries in Europe - America, but also in developing countries like Vietnam. Governments of different countries use planning tools to manage different levels, first of all, the financial source from state budget to invest/sponsorize public colleges, thereby coordinating their activities. these fields follow the predetermined trajectory and target. Accordingly, the renovation and improvement of planning work is an urgent requirement and must be carried out regularly, in

order to improve the management capacity and efficiency of the state, with the basic principles and directions as follows: combine the plan with the market; move from specific, direct plans to directional, indirect plans; improve the quality of planning work, and at the same time strengthen the direction of the implementation of the plan.

(3) The policy instrument is a major tool that the state uses to manage public colleges. In the most general form, each specific policy is a set of certain solutions to realize partial goals in the process towards the common goal of socio-economic development. The basic function of the policy is to create the necessary stimulus to turn the Party's guidelines and directions into reality. Defining "educational development as the top national policy" [115], in recent years many related policies have been promulgated by the state in order to accelerate the process of realizing university autonomy, improve the effectiveness, effective state management of public colleges, such as: socialization policy; investment credit policy; science and technology development policy; Wage policy; the policy of exemption and reduction of tuition fees; scholarship policy for students, students;...

Management methods:

(i) The organizational-administrative approach is the direct influence of the state through a decisive and binding decision on public colleges, in order to realize specific objectives in certain situations. certain situation. The organizational-administrative approach affects public colleges in two directions: the impact on the organization, and the impact on regulating the actions (behavior) of public colleges. In the direction of organizational impact, the state builds and constantly improves the legal framework, creating a "safe legal corridor" for public colleges to operate with peace of mind. Using the administrative method is only highly effective when the decision has a scientific basis, is fully justified in economic terms, and the state only makes the decision on the basis of ensuring sufficient information and integrity. fully account for the interests and related aspects (rights - interests of actors in society). In particular, when using the administrative method, the authority and responsibility of the decision-making body must be firmly attached, avoiding abuse of power, subjectivity, and group interests.

(ii) The economic method is a way of indirectly influencing the state (based on instructive economic interests) on public colleges, in order to make the schools interested in the ultimate effect. of activities (outputs), thereby self-consciously and proactively completing assigned tasks, without the constant influence of the state by administrative methods, thereby accelerating progress. the process of implementing university autonomy, including financial autonomy and self-responsibility. The economic method generates close material attention of public colleges, contains many economic stimulus factors, so the impact is very sensitive and flexible, promoting the initiative, creativity and innovation. created by workers and public colleges. This is considered as a best management method to practice savings, combat waste, and improve the efficiency of using financial resources from state budget. In fact, management clearly shows that "assignment" is a good measure to reduce costs, improve productivity, quality and operational efficiency of public colleges. The economic approach expands the right to act, but at the same time increases the economic responsibility of public colleges. The State uses economic methods to influence public colleges in the following directions: general development orientation with specific goals, tasks and targets appropriate to each period; use economic norms (taxes, credit interest rates, etc.) to encourage development.

(iii) The educational method is the way the state affects the perception and feelings of the people under the management, in order to improve their self-discipline, positivity and enthusiasm in working in the practice. perform well on assigned tasks. In the trend of continuing to innovate and constantly improving the operational efficiency of current public non-business units, including public colleges, the propaganda and education to raise awareness, replace Changing management thinking of individual leaders, as well as the obligations and rights of employees through conferences, seminars, mass media, using mass organizations, etc., is the end. necessary efforts, in order to speed up the process of self-realization of public non-business units.

3. The impact of financial management on the performance of public educational institutions

Operational concept, operational efficiency of public educational institutions

Services contribute more than 80% of gross domestic product (GDP) in developed countries; even in developing countries, service sectors are contributing up to 50% of GDP since the beginning of this century (Karmakar, 2008). International trade agreements such as the General Agreement on Trade in Services have defined education as a service industry. The inclusion of the World Trade Organization (WTO) in public services, including education, further strengthens the prophecy that education will be transformed into a more tradable service sector. business).

Kelley and Sharif (2005) observe: "A country's competitiveness is determined by the quality of higher education it can provide to students." Vietnamese educational institutions, while waking up to this new reality, are aiming to meet the needs not only of the domestic segment but also of the international market.

Hackman and Wageman (1995) advocate that total quality management, if properly implemented, can enable organizations to provide the impetus to deal with their ever-changing environment in a sustainable way. Hammersley and Pinnington (1999) proposed total quality management as a systematic and rationalized philosophy for quality management as well as change management in higher education. Besterfield et al. (2003) defined three words including the abbreviation total quality management: "whole" refers to the whole that is made up; "Quality" refers to the level of excellence of a product or service; and "management" refers to an act, art, or manner of handling, controlling, leading, and planning. total quality management in higher education implies improving the quality of the courses, the entry guidelines, the resource management processes and structures, the output of student support services, and the linkage with the world of work and other organizations (Tulsi, 2001). The model supported by proponents of total quality management (Lagrosen et al., 2004; Venkatraman, 2007) in education emphasizes customer satisfaction and continuous improvement. In this study, total quality management in higher education was understood as an approach that allows attention to be focused on core activities (e.g. teaching and learning methods, curriculum modification and resource development) of the university, while improving the overall quality of its processes (e.g. continuous improvement, student learning growth and enhancing the reputation of the institution) to achieve sustainable institutional outcomes and stakeholder satisfaction.

Activities of public educational institutions

To implement total quality management, the top management of higher education institutions (HEIs) should understand the elements - quality aspects - that make up the foundation of total quality management (Ardi et al., 2012) . Although previous experimental studies have explored the constitutive quality dimensions of total quality management structures in HEI (Ardi et al., 2012), there seems to be disagreement regarding the formation dimensions. this structure (Soria-Garcia and Martinez-Lorente, 2014). Therefore, different attributes and frameworks for total quality management have been proposed (Mehta et al., 2014), including interdependent factors, namely principles, values, factors importance, size, composition or composition (Fotopoulos and Psomas, 2009).

According to Venkatraman (2007), the fundamental core values that form the building blocks of the total quality management framework for the higher education environment are: leadership and a culture of quality, continuous improvement and innovation within education processes, employee engagement and development, agile response and information management, customer-based quality, and partnership development. After reviewing the literature, O'Mahony and Garavan (2012) state that factors relevant to understanding the implementation of quality management systems in higher education include commitment and funding from top leadership (communicating a clear mission statement, using empowering access to and using timely data, information, and knowledge of best practices), stakeholder engagement relevant (employee empowerment, middle management involvement) and create a culture of continuous improvement and focus on process issues (self-assessments, internal audits, scoring standards, process management, measurement, information and analysis, quality management system accreditation and evidence-based approaches to decision making).

Similarly, Svensson and Klefsjo (2006), based on the literature, stated that there is a common ground of core values that form the framework for total quality management-based self-assessment in education. These values include focus on customers and processes, continuous improvement, fact-based decision making, and employee and leadership commitment. Ali and associates. (2010) identified ten important elements of total quality management, related to quality initiatives in the context of university education. These are visionary leadership, customer focus, effective communication, consistent goals, staff selection and deployment, competent staff, teamwork, training, and education, recognition and motivation as well as innovation and creativity. The total quality management framework for engineering education by Mehta et al. (2014) includes institutional resource management, long-term strategy and planning, excellence in human resource management, continuous assessment and improvement, top management commitment and visionary leadership, vision, student focus, employee focus, alumni focus, information management systems, quality mission and vision statement, service culture, philosophy and academic methods innovation and partnerships within industry and organizations

The authors strongly recommend that a combination of total quality management frameworks be implemented for future studies on total quality management (Mehta et al., 2014). The present study took this view and incorporated the most common total quality management elements running through the various frameworks identified in the literature describing total quality management in the education industry. Table I presents the framework of total quality management elements developed as well as supporting documents from the field of total quality management in education. This framework includes the following fundamental elements of total quality management: commitment from top management and leadership, strategic quality planning, faculty, management and staff, supplier management, student focus, process management, continuous improvement, information and analysis, knowledge and education. It should be noted that the theoretical framework of total quality management of this study is consistent with the theoretical framework of the studies of Owlia and Aspinwall (1997), Bayraktar et al. (2008), Ah-Teck and Starr (2013) and Soria-Garcia and Martinez-Lorente (2014) in the field of education.

Many reports have documented the benefits and outcomes of applying total quality management principles in various colleges and universities (Tsinidou et al., 2010). Without a doubt, the benefits of total quality management in service industries such as education are no less than in manufacturing industries, if applied and applied properly (Thakkar et al., 2006). In other words, total quality management principles and tools can make a real difference as far as the success and performance of universities is concerned (Rosa et al., 2001).

According to Saiti (2012), there is a significant impact of total quality management on the improvement mechanisms and outcomes in education, contributing to the economy and society of a country. Ardi and associates. (2012), reviewing the literature, determined that total quality management can make significant contributions to HEIs, such as financial savings, improved morale, improved performance, improved responsiveness, improve customer service and processes, and develop a sense of teamwork. Venkatraman (2007) states that in higher education, total quality management is considered a process-oriented approach to increase productivity, reduce costs and improve service quality. Grant and associates. (2004) notes that universities implement total quality management to improve teaching, measure student satisfaction, improve curriculum, measure staff satisfaction, and improve operations. of the university. Talib et al. (2013) studied the benefits of total quality management in service industries in terms of process and service quality, employee service quality, employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction and performance of the provider. Fraser et al. (2013) identified the benefits of total quality management in service organizations such as improved productivity, higher customer satisfaction, improved employee morale, improved labor-management relations and overall higher performance. According to Oakland (2011), evidence should be provided that the results achieved from the implementation of total quality management are tangible and long-lasting. This evidence should not be limited to operating, financial or market results that demonstrate the results of past performance. It should also include results from other stakeholders, which serve as a leading indicator of future key/financial

performance as measured by excellence in customer satisfaction and loyalty, customer, human motivation and competence, and broader community satisfaction (Oakland, 2011).

The present study follows the suggestion of Oakland (2011) and is similar to that of Calvo-Mora et al. (2005) in the education sector, building on all the outcomes that can be achieved through the implementation of total quality management (improvement of service quality, operational, financial and market efficiency, improved satisfaction of students, faculty and staff and positive impact on society).

The content aspects of quality management are as follows:

1. Commitment of leaders and top leaders

HEI's top leadership:

Prioritize process and service quality over quantity

Actively participate in quality improvement efforts and communicate the commitment to quality to faculty and staff. Put quality issues on the manager's agenda

Motivate and empower faculty and staff to manage and address quality issues

Support quality improvement by providing necessary resources

Lo and Sculli (1996), Johnson and Golomski (1999), Kanji et al. (1999a), Kanji et al. (1999b), Osseo-Asare and Longbottom (2002), Calvo-Mora et al. (2005), Osseo-Asare et al. (2005), Calvo-Mora et al. (2006), Venkatraman (2007), Bayraktar et al. (2008), O'Mahony and Garavan (2012), Ardi et al. (2012), Calvo-Mora et al. (2014)

2. Strategic quality planning

Quality policy considered in strategic planning

Student requirements and expectations are considered in planning processes and services

The institution sets quality goals for administrators, faculty, and staff

Quality objectives and policies are communicated throughout the organization

Quality goals are set based on student needs and requirements

Process outputs are compared with the organization's objectives

Osseo-Asare and Longbottom (2002), Calvo-Mora et al. (2005), Calvo-Mora et al. (2006), Venkatraman (2007), O'Mahony and Garavan (2012), Calvo-Mora et al. (2014).

3. Faculty and management and staff involvement

Teachers and staff are evaluated

Data/information collected from faculty and staff about their satisfaction and suggestions for improvement

There are communication channels throughout the facility

Teaching staff and staff participate in meetings and agendas related to quality improvement planning

Faculty and staff with significant quality improvement efforts will be rewarded

Teaching staff and staff take the initiative

Faculty and staff are involved in decision making and setting quality goals Faculty and staff are motivated to improve their performance

Lo and Sculli (1996), Johnson and Golomski (1999), Kanji et al. (1999a), Kanji et al. (1999b), Osseo-Asare and Longbottom (2002), Osseo-Asare et al. (2005), CalvoMora et al. (2005), Calvo-Mora et al. (2006), Venkatraman (2007), Bayraktar et al. (2008), Calvo-Mora et al. (2014), Soria-Garcia and Martinez-Lorente (2014)

4. Supplier management

Specifications are clearly defined by the organization for suppliers

The organization's suppliers are not many

The organization has strong and long-standing relationships with suppliers

The evaluation and selection of suppliers is mainly based on the issue of quality rather than cost

Suppliers participate in the organization's quality improvement efforts

Calvo-Mora et al. (2005), Calvo-Mora et al. (2006), SoriaGarcia and Martinez-Lorente (2014)

5. Student focus

Student complaints, satisfaction and quality improvement suggestions are identified and analyzed

Administrators are in close contact with students and have a close relationship with them

Student needs, requirements, wants and expectations are recorded and analyzed

Faculty members are in close contact with students and have a strong relationship with them

Students are encouraged to submit complaints and suggestions for quality improvement

Institutional goals exceed student expectations

Lo and Sculli (1996), Johnson and Golomski (1999), Kanji et al. (1999a), Kanji et al. (1999b), Osseo-Asare and Longbottom (2002), Calvo-Mora et al. (2006), Venkatraman (2007), Bayraktar et al. (2008), Ardi et al. (2012), O'Mahony and Garavan (2012)

6. Process management (education, research and administration)

Work instructions are provided to faculty and staff

Nonconformities of processes and services detected through internal audit

Critical quality processes are identified and their performance evaluated

Preventive maintenance of equipment is performed regularly

Mistakes are eliminated in the design of processes

Lo and Sculli (1996), Johnson and Golomski (1999), Osseo-Asare and Longbottom (2002), Calvo-Mora et al. (2005), Calvo-Mora et al. (2006), Venkatraman (2007), Bayraktar et al. (2008), O'Mahony and Garavan (2012), Calvo-Mora et al. (2014), Soria-Garcia and Martinez Lorete (2014)

7. Continuous improvement

Areas in the organization and procedures for improvement are identified

Processes and services are continuously researched and improved

Waste sources (e.g. defects, waiting, inappropriate handling) are detected to minimize the cost of internal processes

Kanji et al. (1999a), Johnson and Golomski (1999), Kanji et al. (1999b), Bayraktar et al. (2008), O'Mahony and Garavan (2012)

8. Information and analysis

Quality data reviewed from top management in the decision-making process

Quality data is considered by managers during planning and control

Quality data reviewed by faculty and staff in their daily work

Quality data (e.g. defects, nonconformities) and organizational performance indicators recorded and analyzed

Based on benchmarking, the organization's performance is compared with the performance of the top and best performing organizations and their best practices are reviewed.

Lo and Sculli (1996), Johnson and Golomski (1999), Kanji et al. (1999a, 1999b), Venkatraman (2007), O'Mahony and Garavan (2012), Soria-Garcia and Martinez-Lorente (2014)

9. Knowledge and education

Faculty and staff are trained in topics relevant to their profession and day-to-day work The faculty and staff have the right knowledge and know-how Trained faculty and staff in quality management and problem-solving techniques Resources are provided for educational purposes Educational programs are evaluated.

Lo and Sculli (1996), Kanji et al. (1999b), Calvo-Mora et al. (2005), Venkatraman (2007), Bayraktar et al. (2008), O'Mahony and Garavan (2012), Soria-Garcia and Martinez-Lorente (2014)

*: Scales are measured using a 7-point Likert scale, in which 1 level is absolutely zero, 2 levels are very low, 3 levels are low, 4 are average, 5 are high, 6 are very high, 7 are extremely high .

3.3.3. Criteria for evaluating the performance of public educational institutions

Measured through 5 aspects measured by a 7-point Likert scale, in which 1 level is absolutely not, 2 levels are very low, 3 levels are low, 4 are average, 5 are high, 6 are very high, and 7 levels extremely high.

1. Reputation and image of the organization

The extent to which:

- (i) The organization succeeds in creating a culture of learning and growth.
- (ii) The reputation and image of the organization has increased over the past three years.
- (iii) The quality (academic outcomes) of students joining your institution has improved over the past three years.
- (iv) The percentage of students studying further has increased over the past three years.
- (v) Overall student achievement has increased, and improved, over the past three years.

2. Quality of infrastructure

The extent to which:

- (i) Your organization's infrastructure, which has grown and improved, over the past three years.
- (ii) The proportion of library resources (number of books and journals) increased and improved over the years.
- (iii) Laboratory equipment (seats and laboratory equipment) has increased and improved over the past three years.
- (iv) The entry of computer media has increased, and improved, over the past three years.

3. The excellence of the faculty

The extent to which:

- (i) The organization is successful in achieving the overall vision, mission, strategic plans and stated objectives.
- (ii) The student-faculty ratio in your institution has improved, over the past three years.
- (iii) The overall performance level of faculty members has increased in terms of: commitment to continuous improvement in quality and excellence.
- (iv) The overall level of performance of the faculty has increased in terms of: guidance and counseling for students.
- (v) The overall level of performance of faculty members has increased in terms of: excellence in academic activities (including teaching, research implementation of continuing education programs and consulting).

4. Research and industry exposure

The extent to which:

- (i) The excellence of research-based and industry-based projects undertaken by faculty and students over the past three years.
- (ii) Strengthen research activities and publish research articles in journals and conferences, patents, awards and prizes won by faculty and students over the past three years.
- (iii) The quality of placement has increased over the past three years (in terms of number of students placed, how good placement offers are made, etc.).
- (iv) Interfaces and industry partnerships have grown and strengthened over the past three years.

5. Satisfaction of stakeholders

On your organization's overall performance over the past three years:

- (i) Increase the satisfaction of: your students.
- (ii) Increase the satisfaction level of: your employees.
- (iii) Increase the satisfaction of: your alumni.
- (iv) Increase the satisfaction of: your student's employer.
- (v) Increase the satisfaction of: your student's parents.

4. CONCLUSION

In the trend of transitioning to an autonomous mechanism, the issue of financial exploitation and effective use of financial resources for the operation of public colleges plays a very important role. A high degree of financial autonomy helps public colleges increase revenue and use mobilized capital, effectively meeting spending needs

for the school's operations. Management is a behavior of the subject expressed through the formulation of plans, organizing the implementation of the plan, checking and adjusting activities to achieve the objectives of the subject.

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